

Bi-directional Interoperability Between Architectural and Structural BIM for Efficient Structural Design and Analysis

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Abstract

Building Information Modelling (BIM) has revolutionized the construction industry's digital representation of physical building elements. Despite the transformative potential, the main obstacles to better collaboration are issues related to interoperability between architectural and structural modelling platforms. Therefore, we study interoperability between BIM environments with an emphasis on the analysis of the effectiveness of bi-directional links based on IFC (Industry Foundation Classes).

The purpose of this research is to assess the interoperability between architectural and structural models and the related impact on the effectiveness of design, modelling, and analysis using BIM. To achieve these goals, the methodology used includes a detailed analysis of the capabilities of BIM environments and Finite Element Modelling (FEM) which are tested using practical workflow on real-life projects. The study evaluates the interoperability between the Autodesk Revit (BIM) and the ProtaStructure (FEM) platforms with the ProtaBIM add-on and IFC, which enables two-way connections.

This research contributes to a better understanding of interoperability and aims to improve the cooperation between the architectural and construction professions by increasing the efficiency of work with BIM, and at the same time, aiming to reduce the scope of errors, delays, and costs. The results are important for designers and other project stakeholders, as well as contribute to the analysis and development of IFC which pave the way to future initiatives by researchers and BIM software developers with the goal of improving interoperability between professions.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/EBkIAeh0Wc0>

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